

Digital Dentures: Simplifying complete denture fabrication

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Abstract:- Complete denture fabrication has traditionally involved multiple appointments and technique-sensitive laboratory procedures, often leading to processing errors and time consumption. The digital revolution in prosthodontics has simplified this workflow through the integration of intraoral scanning, virtual jaw relation records, CAD designing, and CAM manufacturing via milling or 3D printing. Digital dentures offer improved accuracy, better fit, reduced polymerization shrinkage, and enhanced patient comfort. The ability to store digital records enables easy reproduction without repeating initial procedures, improving efficiency and predictability. Although the initial investment and learning curve remain challenges, digital technology enhances communication between clinician and laboratory while reducing chair side time. This paradigm shift from conventional to digital methods represents a significant advancement in complete denture therapy, ensuring precision-driven and patient-centered outcomes.

Keywords:- *Digital complete denture, CAD CAM, Digital dentistry, Removable prosthodontics, Denture fabrication*

Introduction:-

Recent advancements in digital dentistry have significantly influenced removable prosthodontics, particularly in the fabrication of complete dentures. Digital complete denture workflows utilize computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing (CAD-CAM) technologies to improve accuracy, reduce clinical visits, and enhance patient comfort.

A comprehensive review by Geghamyan et AL. highlighted the evolution of digital complete dentures and emphasized their advantages over conventional methods, including improved fit, standardized fabrication, and digital record storage for future reproduction. Furthermore, a recent systematic review evaluating cost-efficiency and patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) demonstrated that digitally fabricated complete dentures are associated with reduced chair side time and high patient satisfaction when compared to conventional dentures. These findings justify the growing relevance and clinical adoption of digital complete dentures in contemporary prosthodontics practice.¹⁻⁶

Fabrication of conventional complete dentures is a complex restoration method, that requires a significant time and typically involving primary impression, secondary impressions, jaw relation records, clinical try in, and complete denture insertion, which has been used for nearly century without change⁷. Now a days complete dentures can be constructed using traditional methods, and be simplified by computer programs like cad cam, not only to decrease the no of patients visit but also to produce a very efficient complete denture⁸. The greater efficiency, reduced clinic visits, decreased sitting chair time, elimination of denture base polymerization shrinkage, and ability to fabricate additional dentures with existing saved data are key advantages of digital complete denture.⁷

The preservation of natural teeth remains a fundamental objective of digital dentistry. However, the likelihood of tooth loss increases with age. Consequently, Edentalism, together with rising life expectancy, has resulted in a steadily growing demand for both partial and complete dentures.⁹ Recent advancements in digital technologies have greatly enhanced dental practice, enabling clinicians to deliver optimal treatment in a more efficient and comfortable manner. These technologies provide extensive options for maintaining oral health and restoring function and aesthetics to a level that closely resembles natural dentition. Benefits include a streamlined clinical workflow, shorter treatment duration, improved quality control, and reduced risk of procedural errors.¹⁰ Polymerization shrinkage remains a significant concern in denture fabrication. To address this issue, numerous investigations have focused on improving denture base materials, refining fabrication techniques, and modifying clinical procedures such as laboratory remounting. Furthermore, to minimize inaccuracies associated

with conventional complete dentures, computer-aided design (CAD) and computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) technologies have been incorporated into prosthodontics. Owing to their precision, automation, and enhanced efficiency, CAD/CAM systems have become widely adopted for the fabrication of various dental prostheses. The production of complete dentures using CAD/CAM technology has evolved substantially with continuous advancements in digital equipment and specialized software, leading to greater accuracy, consistency, and predictability in clinical outcomes.¹¹

New milling techniques and modern polymethylmethacrylates (PMMA) resins have improved fitting accuracy of denture bases, which is a key factor for effective complete dentures. Goodacre ET AL demonstrated that milled denture bases produced using digital technology had better accuracy compared with conventionally manufactured CDs.¹² CAD/CAM produces dentures with better fit than conventional dentures.¹³

Evolution of Digital dentures:-

In the early 1990s, the first attempts to fabricate complete dentures using CAD/CAM Technology utilizing 3D laser scanning and milling techniques were reported. In 2000s, advancements in intraoral scanning and three-dimensional printing technologies led to the development of several digital denture systems, such as DentCAD /CAM denture system and the Ava Dent digital denture system. In the 2010s, the introduction of new materials and improvements in digital workflows further expanded the application of digital technologies in complete denture fabrication.¹⁴

The digitization of complete denture (CD) fabrication began with the development of specialized CAD software, which enabled the computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) of denture bases and artificial teeth through either subtractive or additive processes.¹⁵ The incorporation of intraoral scanning into complete denture fabrication has the potential to enhance patient comfort, improve clinical ergonomics, and increase laboratory efficiency.¹⁶ Make intraoral scans of the maxillary and mandibular dental arches by using an intraoral scanner.¹⁷

A fully digital approach transferring the position of maxillary dentition to a virtual articulator by using intraoral scans and CBCT scans. This digital approach eliminates the traditional face bow transfer and mounting process and the complex procedures necessary to evaluate mandibular positional changes, centric relation occlusion to maximal intercuspation position.¹⁸ These technological advancements have provided component methods to facilitate fast and accurate fabrication of bases.

Digital Work flow in complete denture fabrication:-

Data Acquisition:-

Digital impression:- The intraoral scanner used to scan the dental arches upper and lower jaw. The lips were retracted with a cheek holder and saliva constantly removed with a suction during intraoral scanning. An occlusal rim and the physiological rest posture served as the orientation for the occlusal vertical dimension.

Digitized extra-orally with scanner.

The obtained virtual design was used to produce two final denture sets utilizing the following technical approaches.¹⁵

Computer aided design(CAD):-

Digital denture design :from data integration to virtual articulation.

This method involves merging facial scan or CBCT data with intraoral scan data and applying a virtual articulator based on recorded TMJ position²⁰. The use of virtual articulator not only eliminates the cumbersome gypsum mounting process of the past but also avoids the errors that occur during this process, making it a very efficient digital protocol²¹.

The incisive papillae, hamular notch, retromolar pad, and approximate canine positions are used. Most CAD software sets tooth arrangement based on these.

Figure 1. Intraoral scanner Prime scan

Artificial tooth arrangement:-

Artificial teeth of appropriate sizes are selected and arranged considerably the aesthetics of the anterior region and the occlusion between maxilla and mandible. In particular for mandibular Edentulous patients, for stability, the posterior cusps should be located within the triangle connecting the canine area to the left and right retromolar pads depending on the position.¹⁴

The length, width and height of dentition could be adjusted, and the localization of the dentition could be modified accordingly to match the arch shapes of the individual.²²

All the available functions mentioned above were used to arrange teeth in 3D virtual models to match particular shape of patient arches.

Figure 2. Computer aided designing

Figure 3. Computer aided designing

Cam process:-

Consideration of a one-piece or two-piece denture

The design of digital dentures is largely divided into two categories: whether the teeth and base are separated or not. . Since the used teeth and base have different colors, the basic method is to fabricate them separately. However, to eliminate the errors that occur when combining the teeth and base and for convenience of fabrication, a one-piece method is sometimes used.²²

Milling process:-

The CAM procedure, which employs milling machines, is currently a standard way of producing prostheses in dentistry. Burs that move over two or three axes in 3D space act similarly to how a dentist prepares a tooth. Recently, 5-axis milling machines were created, which move both the tool and the disc or block material, enabling for more precise prosthesis production. Specifically, the utilization of different bur forms has made it feasible to replicate the border or internal irregularity of dentures, and convenience features like as automatic block replacement systems and discs containing two or more materials have been developed.

In the case of digital dentures, most are made of poly-methyl methacrylate (PMMA), and the advantages of various PMMA disc materials developed long ago can be directly utilized. Relatively recently developed 3D printing materials with uncertain long-term follow-up results are expected to yield more stable and better outcomes.²³

Figure 4. Milling the prostheses

3D Printing:-

Additive manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing, has become one of the pillars of digital technology in the dental field of prosthodontics.²⁴ 3D printing is not only much more economical than milling because there is no material to be cut away but also has no limitations in shape due to the limitations of the cutting tool, allowing for the production of very freely shaped products. This idea, developed around 1980, has been treated as a groundbreaking solution to overcome both the manufacturing technology and economics of the past and has been developed and used in various parts of the dental industry as well as general manufacturing industries.

In dentistry, 3D printing is considered to be a suitable production method for dentures, which are the main area of Edentalism surfaces, especially due to of the absence of shape limitations with this technique.²⁵

Figure 5. Complete Denture Prostheses-Delivery of denture

ADVANTAGES OF COMPLETE DENTURE DIGITILIZATION:

- 1.Increased efficiency,Automaticity
- 2.Accuracy of entire treatment flow
- 3.Fabrication process has become simpler
- 4.Precision,Reduced number of appointments

Limitations and challenges in full digital workflow:-

Despite the advantages of digital complete dentures, several limitations and challenges persist. A scoping review on functional impressions in digital workflows reported difficulties in accurately capturing movable soft tissues and functional borders in completely Edentalism arches using purely digital techniques. As a result, hybrid workflows combining conventional impressions with digital processing are often recommended.

Additionally, a systematic review on complications of 3D-printed dentures identified issues such as surface roughness, wear resistance, fracture risk, and need for post-insertion adjustments. These limitations highlight that although digital dentures offer efficiency and reproducibility, careful case selection, material choice, and clinician expertise are essential for successful outcomes.

Clinical applications:-

Materials and Physical Properties (supporting evidence)

The physical and mechanical properties of digitally fabricated denture base materials play a crucial role in their clinical success. An in-vitro study published in BMC Oral Health compared CAD-CAM denture base resins with conventionally processed acrylic resins and reported superior flexural strength, reduced porosity, and improved dimensional stability in digitally fabricated materials. These enhanced material properties may contribute to better fit, durability, and long-term performance of digital complete dentures.

Future prospectus:-

Lastly Digital dentures are relevant today because evidence shows better material properties, high patient satisfaction, and reduced clinical time, although challenges remain in functional impressions and long-term complications.”

Conclusion:-

The digital revolution has transformed complete denture fabrication from a labor-intensive, technique-sensitive procedure into a streamlined, precision-driven workflow. By integrating CAD-CAM technology, virtual records, and advanced manufacturing techniques, digital dentures enhance accuracy, reduce clinical visits, and improve patient comfort and satisfaction. The ability to store and reproduce digital data further adds predictability and long-term efficiency to treatment.

Although cost and training remain initial challenges, the advantages of consistency, reduced errors, and improved communication between clinician and laboratory outweigh these limitations. Digital complete denture fabrication is not merely an innovation but a paradigm shift—redefining simplicity, precision, and excellence in modern prosthodontic care.

References:-

- (1) .Geghamyan S, Zurabyan A, Heboyan A. Digital complete dentures: An updated comprehensive review. *Bulletin of Stomatology and Maxillofacial Surgery*. 2025;21(1):155–167. – A recent comprehensive review on digital complete dentures, covering workflow, materials, advantages, and challenges. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- (2) .Systematic review on cost-efficiency & PROMs:Digitally versus conventionally fabricated complete dentures: A systematic review on cost-efficiency analysis and patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs). *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2025. – Compares digital vs conventional dentures in terms of cost, clinical time, patient satisfaction, and outcomes. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- (3) .CAD-CAM vs conventional denture bases (in vitro): CAD-CAM vs conventional denture bases: systematic review with network meta-analysis of mechanical properties. *Frontiers in Dental Medicine*. 2025. – In-depth review of material properties of digitised milled and printed denture bases. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- (4) .Scoping review on functional impressions:Functional impression of complete edentulous arches in a digital flow: A scoping review. *Journal of Dentistry*. 2025. – Discusses challenges and hybrid workflows related to capturing functional impressions in full digital denture workflows. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- (5) .Systematic review on complications:Complications of 3D printed dentures: A systematic review. *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2025. – Focuses on complications and post-insertion visits related to digitally fabricated dentures. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- (6) .Patient perception pilot study (preprint):Patient Perception on Digital Complete Dentures Compared with Conventional Complete Dentures. *preprints.org* 2025 – Early evidence on patient satisfaction differences between digital and conventional dentures.
- (7) .Kehui Deng, Hu Chen, Yong Wang, Yongsheng Zhou, Yuchun Sun Year: 2021 Container: The journal of advanced prosthodontics Volume: 13 Issue: 6 Page: 361-361 DOI: 10.4047/jap.2021.13.6.361\
- (8) .Abd El Galil EG, Mohamed SL, Rizk FN, Sabet ME. Evaluation of two computer-aided design software on the adaptation of digitally constructed maxillary complete denture. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc* [Internet]. 2021;21(4):383–90. Available from: http://dx.doi.org/10.4103/jips.jips_137_21
- (9) .Mdpi.com. [cited 2025 Apr 23]. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-1592/3/3/23>
- (10) .Manu rathee,sanju malil,rahul kumar raman,prachi jain,smriti kaushik,renu kundu:Digitilization in prosthodontics :changing needs based on modern demands Volume 1 issue 3 2021
- (11) . Lee S, Hong S-J, Paek J, Pae A, Kwon K-R, Noh K. Comparing accuracy of denture bases fabricated by injection molding, CAD/CAM milling, and rapid prototyping method. *J Adv Prosthodont* [Internet]. 2019;11(1):55–64. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4047/jap.2019.11.1.55>
- (12) .Ciocca L, Maltauro M, Cimini V, Breschi L, Montanari A, Anderlucci L, et al. Analysis of the trueness and precision of complete denture bases manufactured using digital and analog technologies. *J Adv Prosthodont* [Internet]. 2023;15(1):22–32. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4047/jap.2023.15.1.22>
- (13) .Otto steismaall et.al ,Cad cam produces denture with improved fit :2018

- (14) .park C. A comprehensive narrative review exploring the current landscape of digital complete denture technology and advancements. Heliyon [Internet]. 2025;11(2):e41870. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2025.e41870>
- (15) .Unkovskiy A, Wahl E, Zander AT, Huettig F, Spintzyk S. Intraoral scanning to fabricate complete dentures with functional borders: a proof-of-concept case report. BMC Oral Health [Internet]. 2019;19(1):46. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12903-019-0733-5>
- (16) .Lo Russo L, Salamini A, Troiano G, Guida L. Digital dentures: A protocol based on intraoral scans. J Prosthet Dent [Internet]. 2021;125(4):597–602. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.prosdent.2020.02.006>
- (17) .Lo Russo L, Di Gioia C, Salamini A, Guida L. Integrating intraoral, perioral, and facial scans into the design of digital dentures. J Prosthet Dent [Internet]. 2020;123(4):584–8. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.prosdent.2019.05.030>
- (18) .Park JH, Lee G-H, Moon D-N, Kim J-C, Park M, Lee K-M. A digital approach to the evaluation of mandibular position by using a virtual articulator. J Prosthet Dent [Internet]. 2021;125(6):849–53. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.prosdent.2020.04.002>
- (19) .Wiley.com. [cited 2025 Apr 23]. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1155/2018/5189761>
- (20) .Revilla-León M, Zeitler JM, Kois JC. An overview of the different digital facebow methods for transferring the maxillary cast into the virtual articulator. J Esthet Restor Dent [Internet]. 2024;36(12):1675–86. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/jerd.13264>
- (21) .Kanazawa M, Inokoshi M, Minakuchi S, Ohbayashi N. Trial of a CAD/CAM system for fabricating complete dentures. Dent Mater J [Internet]. 2011;30(1):93–6. Available from: https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dmj/30/1/30_2010-112/article-char
- (22) .Zandinejad A, Floriani F, Lin W-S, Naimi-Akbar A. Clinical outcomes of milled, 3D-printed, and conventional complete dentures in edentulous patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. J Prosthodont [Internet]. 2024;33(8):736–47. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/jopr.13859>
- (23) .Zhan X, Cao L, Xiang D, Tang H, Xia D, Lin H. Effect of printing orientation on physical and mechanical properties of 3D printing prosthodontic base resin materials. Beijing Da Xue Xue Bao. 2024;56(2):345–51
- (24) .sitePunj A. Digital dentistry for complete dentures [Internet]. Decisions in Dentistry. 2020 [cited 2025 Apr 23]
- (25) .Yeslam HE, Freifrau von Maltzahn N, Nassar HM. Revolutionizing CAD/CAM-based restorative dental processes and materials with artificial intelligence: a concise narrative review. PeerJ [Internet]. 2024;12(e17793)<https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.17793>. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7717/peerj.17793>